

THE CULTURE OF USING STABLE PHRASES

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Annotation.

In the vocabulary of Turkmen and English, lexical units in the form of stable phrases consisting of several words and having one meaning as a whole also occupy a significant place. These idiomatic expressions used in speech differ in their emotional-expressive nature, effectiveness, and serve as an artistic means of expressing thoughts in a very concise and figurative way. For example, appropriately used idiomatic expressions such as: *öyli-işikli etmek* (Settle someone down. Get someone married), *ayagyny baglamak (öylendirmek manysynda)* (Tie the knot” (when referring to oneself) Find a spouse for someone), *göze çöp atmak (aldamak manysynda)* (Pull the wool over someone’s eyes. Deceive someone), *ýüzüni gyzdyrmak (utandyrmak manysynda)* give expressiveness and national flavor to the speech.

The use of such phraseological units, which have been refined over the centuries and have become stable in terms of structure and meaning, has also become a norm. They are widely used, especially in folklore and the works of famous wordsmiths, and have become standardized in terms of structure, meaning, and usage. Their use in folklore and the works of famous wordsmiths is presented as a literary norm.

Phraseologisms are usually stable in structure. They cannot be added, removed, or rearranged. That is why they are called stable phraseological units. In some cases, rude words are replaced by more polite ones, such as “*Özi-hä küi üstünde, göwni welin Kap dagynda*” (Living humbly but dreaming big. Physically modest, mentally ambitious) *ýa-da* “*Osal gyza arpa uny-da bahana*” (A bad workman blames his tools. Any excuse will do for the inept).

One of the main criteria for selecting phraseological units is to explain the studied unit with a synonym of the phraseologism in the form of a free phrase that is understandable to students. For example: *Iki ädimlikde – örän golaý – A stone’s throw away. Just around the corner. Very close. Görüşýänçäk – See you soon. Hoş, sag boluň – Goodbye. Farewell. Duşuşýançäk – Until we meet again. See you later. Ertiriň haýyrly – Good morning. Gündiziň haýyrly – Good afternoon. Giç ýagşy – Good evening.*

The simplest form of understanding is always considered to be comparison. Phraseologisms based on comparison do not cause difficulties for English learners. Therefore, it is easy to introduce such phraseologisms at the initial stage. *Guş bazary – bazardaky ýaly goh-galmagal. Like a marketplace. As noisy as a bazaar.*

Phraseological dictionaries play a significant role in the correct and appropriate use of stable vocabulary. Students should make the use of phraseological dictionaries a habit. To achieve this, the teacher can offer students several tasks:

Keywords: *phraseologisms; orthoepic norm; orthographic norm; literary language; phraseological dictionary; translation analysis; to teach; translation; teaching.*

In the vocabulary of Turkmen and English, lexical units in the form of stable phrases consisting of several words and having one meaning as a whole also occupy a significant place. These idiomatic expressions used in speech differ in their emotional-expressive nature, expressiveness, and serve as an artistic means of expressing thoughts in a very concise and figurative way. For example, appropriately used idiomatic expressions such as: *öýli-işikli etmek (Settle someone down. Get someone married)– aýagyny baglamak (öylendirmek manysynda) (Tie the knot” (when referring to oneself) Find a spouse for someone), göze çöp atmak (aldamak manysynda) (Pull the wool over someone’s eyes. Deceive someone), ýüzüni gyzdyrmak (utandyrmak manysynda) (Make someone blush. Embarrass someone), ýoldan çykmak (azmak manysynda) (Go astray. Stray from the path), göz görkezmek (gorkuzmak manysynda) (Show who’s boss. Intimidate), buz üstünden tozan aramak (yrsaramak manysynda) (Split hairs. Look for trouble where there’s none), elipden şermende (sowatsyz manysynda) (Illiterate. Uneducated), eli egri (ogry manysynda) (Have sticky fingers. Be a thief), guş kelle (Bird-brained), aklyly ýeňil (Foolish), beýnisi ýuka (samsyk manysynda) (Featherbrained), başy boş (dul manysynda) (Single. Unmarried. Widowed), telpegi agan (aýaly ýogalan manysynda) (Widowed man. Lost his wife), kör düýesi köprüden geçen (öýlenen manysynda) (Finally settled down. Got married) ... give expressiveness and national flavor to the speech.*

The use of such phraseological units, which have been refined over the centuries and have become stable in terms of structure and meaning, has also become a norm. They are widely used, especially in folklore and the works of famous wordsmiths, and have become standardized in terms of structure, meaning, and usage. Their use in folklore and the works of famous wordsmiths is presented as a literary norm.

Phraseologisms are usually stable in structure. They cannot be added, removed, or rearranged. That is why they are called stable phraseological units. In some cases, rude words are replaced by more polite ones, such as “*Özi-hä küi üstünde, göwni welin Kap dagynda*” (*Living humbly but dreaming big. Physically modest, mentally ambitious*) *ýa-da “Osaly gyza arpa uny-da bahana” (A bad workman blames his tools. Any excuse will do for the inept).*

It is also necessary to observe literary norms regarding the use of stable vocabulary, such as orthoepic and orthographic norms of the literary language. Only when they are used appropriately in accordance with literary norms, the creativity of the work increases, its effectiveness increases. For example, if the norm of use of stable vocabulary of the Turkmen language is reflected in the phraseological dictionary of the Turkmen language, the norm of use of stable vocabulary of the English language is given in the phraseological dictionary of the English language.

In phraseological dictionaries, they are arranged alphabetically by the first word. The meanings of phraseologisms with multiple meanings are given with Arabic numerals. For example: *Adam bolmak* (*Come of age. Grow up and mature*) - 1. *kemala gelmek, yetişmek, ulalmak*. 2. (*Become a respectable person. Join the ranks of the wise*) *sana goşulmak, akyllanmak*.

Variants of phraseologisms are shown in parentheses after the most commonly used form. For example: *Gaş düzetjek* (*bejerjek*) *bolup göz çykarmak* (*Make things worse while trying to fix them. Do more harm than good*). *Adam sanyna girmek* (*goşulmak*) (*Earn respect. Come into one's own. Mature and gain a good reputation*) – *at-abraya eýe bolmak, terbiýelenip yetişmek*. Phraseological units are explained in the same way as in an explanatory dictionary. The meaning of each phraseological unit is explained, its semantic nuances and usage are revealed separately, and they are justified by examples taken from folklore and literary works. For example: *Gözden düşmek* (*Fall from grace. Lose one's reputation. Be disgraced*)– *abraydan gaçmak, masgara bolmak, iliň ýigrenjine galmak*. *Ýoldan çykmak* (*Go astray. Stray from the path. Deviate from proper behavior*) – *biwepalyk etmek, aýagyňy dürs basmazlyk, sandan çykmak, azmak, bozulmak*.

The phraseological dictionary of a language plays a significant role in studying the meanings of stable phraseological units in the language, their usage in the service of artistic means, and in developing the speech culture of the people.

One of the main criteria for selecting phraseological units is to explain the studied unit with a synonym of the phraseologism in the form of a free phrase that is understandable to students. *İki ädimlikde – örän golaý – A stone's throw away. Just around the corner. Very close. Görüşýänçäk – See you soon. Hoş, sag boluň – Goodbye. Farewell. Duşuşýançak – Until we meet again. See you later. Ertiriň haýyrly – Good morning. Gündiziň haýyrly – Good afternoon. Giç ýagşy – Good evening. Hoş geldiňiz – Welcome. Bagyşlaň – Sorry. Excuse me. Noş bolsun – You're. Welcome (after being thanked). Cheers” (when toasting). Bir sözde – gysga In a nutshell. In brief. Biragyzdan – bilelikde. In unison. All together. Ujypsyz – az sanly. A drop in the ocean. A drop in the bucket. Burnuň aşagynda – örän golaý Face to face. Close up. Ýüzbe-ýüz Head-to-head. One-on-one. Elinden dür dökülýär – Hemme zady başarýar Jack of all trades. A versatile person. Dilini tapmak – doly düşünişmek Find common ground. Speak the same language.*

The simplest form of understanding is always considered to be comparison. Phraseologisms based on comparison do not cause difficulties for English learners. Therefore, it is easy to introduce such phraseologisms at the initial stage.

Guş bazary – bazardaky ýaly goh-galmagal. Like a marketplace. As noisy as a bazaar. Bedreden guýýan ýaly . It's raining cats and dogs. Howa ýaly gerek. As essential as air. Need it like I need air to breathe. Aç möjek kimin. Hungry as a wolf. Ravenous like a wolf. Gözüň göreji kimin goramak. Protect like the apple of one's eye. Köre hasa. As clear as two plus two. As simple as two and two make four. Öz öýüňde ýaly duýmak. Make yourself at home. Towşan tüý As timid as a rabbit. Scared like a hare. İňñede oturan ýaly. Sitting on pins and needles.

When working with the comparison of phraseologisms, it is useful to suggest the comparison of English phraseologisms with similar meanings to the native language. The comparative-comparative analysis of the meaning of English phraseologisms and their coincidence with Turkmen phraseologisms is of great importance.

At the initial stage of teaching, it is possible to introduce phraseologisms that are completely familiar to the learner's native language. The main method is full translation, without excluding other methods, such as the use of synonyms known to students of the given phraseological units, the use of pictures relevant to the situation in which they are used. It is also possible to introduce phraseologisms related to the situations or environment in which students are involved.

Köp okan bilmez, köp ýaşan biler. Live and learn. Işiň ugruna bolsun! Break a leg! (Response: "To hell with it!") Aýdanyň gelsin! Good luck! Gaýtalamak-ylmyň enesidir. Repetition is the mother of learning. Ýürek gysgynça – good Friday face Burnuň sokmak (goşulyşmak) –with one's nose in the air. Başyň çykmak – have a good head on one's shoulders Başyň çykmazlyk – not to have a brain in one's head. Paň kelle – empty head. Kädi kelle – a wooden head. Saman kelle – one's head is full of bees.

Introducing stable phrases about friendship and friends: *Dost kynçylykda belli – A friend in need is a friend indeed. Ömürlük dost – Friends till the end. Friends for life. Ýüz manadyň bolandan, ýüz dostuň bolsun – Better to have a hundred friends than a hundred rubles. Donuň täzesi ýagşy, dostuň könesi – Make new friends but keep the old.*

Phraseological dictionaries play a significant role in the correct and appropriate use of stable phraseological units. Dictionaries that explain the meaning of stable phraseological units are called phraseological dictionaries. A phraseological dictionary is also close to an explanatory dictionary in terms of content and structure. For example: *Unity - friendship, agreement, harmony, common purpose (Explanatory dictionary). Unity - a group of people pursuing a common goal, being united (Phrasal dictionary).*

Phraseological dictionary, like other dictionaries, is presented in alphabetical order. For example, the "Phraseological Dictionary of the Turkmen Language", prepared by a group of scientists from the Magtymguly Institute of Language and Literature of the Academy of Sciences of Turkmenistan and published by the "Ylym" publishing house in 1976, provides explanations for phraseological units commonly used in our literary language - stable phraseological units, proverbs - sayings, idiomatic expressions. Students should make using phraseological dictionaries a habit. To achieve this, the teacher can offer students several tasks:

Task 1. Find the meanings of the phraseologisms "to fill the cup of the mind", "to strengthen the waist", "to reach the sky", "to walk on two legs in two days", "to take care of yourself", "to be like a mulberry tree" in the phraseological dictionary and copy the English equivalent into your notebook.

Task 2. Read the phraseologisms and explain their meanings.

1. Understanding black and white

What he does is good, master

2. Lose yourself	To promise something, to make a covenant
3. To build a family	To recover from illness
4. To listen	Distinguishing between good and evil
5. To promise	Make to do as you please.
6. Light-handed (about medicine)	Listening attentively
7. To be like a mulberry tree	To hurry, haste, to be anxious
8. To speak up	To be married, to start a family

Get the worse of it, they can put anything across me, the devil will carry you off, to spit on the ceiling, he's so gaga.

Task 3. *Read the phraseologisms and find their meanings given on the right, try to find the English equivalent.*

Task 4. *Copy the given phraseologies into your notebook and explain their meaning.*

Play cat and mouse, fierce as a tiger, to cry wolf, wolf in sheep's clothing, fox in the henhouse, be like a bear with a sore head, hungry as a bear, escape the bear and fall to the lion, To roar like a lion, work the rabbit's foot on

Task 5. *Find five sentences from works of art that contain stable phrases and explain their use.*

Task 6. *Find phraseologisms from the English phraseological dictionary that express the concepts of promise, flattery, annoyance, anger, fatigue, and joy, and copy them into your notebook.*

We hope that the above examples will serve as a useful guide for future English language teachers.

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